

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of *o*-Azoaniline

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The current methods of preparation of *o*-azoaniline, based on mild oxidation of *o*-phenylenediamine¹ and electrolytic reduction of *o*-nitroacetanilide² have certain limitations. The former method is not suitable for large scale preparations in view of the requirement of considerable amount of solvent and oxidising agent, while in the latter, the yield is poor and special equipment is required. Attempts to prepare *o*-azoaniline, by reduction of *o*-nitroaniline with zinc and methanolic potassium hydroxide³ invariably result in *o*-phenylenediamine. Even the protection of the amino group of *o*-nitroaniline by acetylation, leads to the same product, evidently due to the hydrolysis of acetyl group during reaction. The present communication describes in detail the preparation of the title compound by reduction of *o*-nitroacetanilide in neutral medium.

***o*-Azoxyacetanilide:** To *o*-nitroacetanilide⁴ (10 g.) and ammonium chloride (7 g.) stirred vigorously in alcohol (400 ml., 46%) in a three-necked flask, zinc dust (10 g.) was slowly added over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was kept stirred for about 2 hrs. more and then filtered. The precipitate (containing zinc) was extracted with hot methyl cellosolve (or dimethyl formamide). The residue after removal of the solvent under vacuum was crystallised from alcohol fractionally to give first *o*-azoxyacetanilide⁵ (m.p. 271°C) and then *o*-azoxyacetanilide⁶ (m.p. 185°C). The filtrate was heated with stirring on a water bath to remove alcohol to give additional crop of *o*-azoxyacetanilide. The total yield was about 90-95%.

***o*-Azoacetanilide:** *o*-Azoxyacetanilide (5 g.) intimately mixed with iron powder (15 g.) (purified by washing with alcohol and ether and then drying) was slowly heated in a cylindrical flask to 220°C and maintained for 2 hrs. at that temperature. The product was extracted with methyl cellosolve (or dimethyl formamide), and after removal of the solvent, crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 271°C. The yield was about 65%.

***o*-Azoaniline:** *o*-Azoacetanilide was hydrolysed with alcoholic KOH/NaOH to yield *o*-azoaniline⁴, m.p. 134°C.

1. Willstätter and Pfannenstiel, *Ber.*, 1900, **39**, 2350.
2. Brand and Stehr, *Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 4061.
3. Feiser and Fisser, "Advanced Organic Chemistry", 1961, p. 690; Vogel, "A Text Book of Organic Chemistry", 1959, p. 681.
4. Witt and Utermann, *Ber.*, 1900, **39**, 3901.
5. Hellbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 1943, 634.
6. *Ibid.*, p. 635.

Effect of Time & Temperature: The influence of various factors on the yield of azoxy and azo compounds was studied. It is seen that maximum yield was obtained after 2 hrs. of reaction (Table I).

TABLE I

Time (hrs.)	% Yield	
	<i>o</i> -azoacetanilide	<i>o</i> -azoxyacetanilide
0.5	2	48
1	2	58
2	14	80
4	4	72

Higher reaction temperatures (Table 2) lowered the yield to 32.5%. The yield was not affected by inert atmosphere, maintained by bubbling of nitrogen gas through the reaction mixture.

TABLE 2

Temp.	Time (hrs.)	<i>o</i> -Azooacetanilide	<i>o</i> -Azoxyacetanilide % recovery
160°C	2	nil	00
210°C	2	80	nil
235°C	0.5	25	nil

Higher temperatures and longer times resulted in the decomposition and charring of the material.

Our grateful thanks are due to Dr. W. D. Patwardhan, Director, for his keen interest and encouragement. Our thanks are also due to Mr. D. V. Sindker and Mrs. P. S. Deshpande for technical assistance.